

Explaining decisions of a light weight deep network model for Coronary Artery Disease classification in Magnetic Resonance Imaging

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Abstract

In certain healthcare settings such as emergency or critical care units, where quick and accurate real-time analysis and decision-making are required, the healthcare system can leverage the power of artificial intelligence (AI) models to support decision-making and prevent complications. This paper investigates the optimization of healthcare AI models based on time complexity, hyper-parameter tuning, and XAI for a classification task. The paper highlights the significance of a lightweight convolutional neural network (CNN) alone or in combination with other classifiers, e.g., CNN-Random-Forest (CNN-RF) for analysing and classifying Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI). The role of hyper-parameter is also examined in finding optimal configurations that enhance the model's performance while efficiently utilizing the limited computational resources. Finally, the benefits of incorporating the XAI technique (GradCAM) in providing transparency and interpretable explanations of AI model predictions, fostering trust, and error/bias detection are explored. Using the proposed model, clinicians/cardiologists can achieve accurate and reliable results while ensuring patient's safety and answering questions imposed by GDPR. The proposed investigative study will advance the understanding and acceptance of AI systems in healthcare settings.

Proposed Work

Figure 1: Proposed Model Architecture

Motivation behind the proposed work is to propose a lightweight deep network model.

- Reduce training and inference time and complexity while maintaining accuracy, enabling real-time or near-real-time CAD diagnosis.
- Exploring different hyper-parameter settings to identify configurations that maximize the model's performance.
- To understand why certain decisions are made, implemented GradCam an XAI technique to provide interpretable insights into the decision-making process of the model, generating heat maps that highlight the contributing regions of MRI / CMR images for the classification of CAD into specific category.

Dataset Description and Performance Matrices

Dataset description:

- Dataset consists of 63,151 multiparametric CMR images that include 37,290 healthy images and 25,861 CAD patients.
- CAD diagnosis was confirmed by invasive coronary angiography.
- During the pre-processing stage, a manual inspection was conducted on images from both subsets, and any images with poor MRI/CMR quality were excluded from further analysis.
- Following the pre-processing stage, the dataset consisted of **34,216** images from healthy patients and **17,438** images from patients with CAD.

Performance Assessment Matrices:

Classification performance is assessed using Positive Predictive Value (PPV), Recall (Sensitivity or True Positive Rate), Specificity (True Negative Rate), F1-Score, Area Under the Curve (AUC), Accuracy and Balanced Accuracy.

Results

Results of Time Complexity Comparison:

Our inference time on a MacBook laptop for 323 test images of size 100x100 is only 2.6 sec, which is only 8 milliseconds per image. Additionally, it provides better or equal classification accuracy. Our model's lower computational complexity enables faster image analysis and diagnosis, improving efficiency, and facilitating deployment on resource-constrained systems.

Results of Hyper-parameter tuning:

Table 1: Model performances achieved with different settings: Comparison

Model	Activation Function	Optimizer	PPV	Recall	Specificity	F1-Score	AUC	Accuracy
Our Model 1	PReLU	Adam	99.19	98.03	99.59	98.60	99.88	99.06
Our Model 2	PReLU	RMSprop	99.62	98.45	99.81	99.04	99.92	99.35
CNN-RF	ReLU	Adam	100	98.88	99.66	99.70	99.00	99.18

Results of Explainability using GradCAM:

Figure 2: Heatmaps generated by GradCAM on test images

Conclusion and Future Direction

The proposed investigative work aimed to provide insights into the optimization of healthcare AI models. ensuring accurate and reliable results with a small lightweight convolutional neural network while prioritizing patient safety and advancing the acceptance and understanding of AI in healthcare settings. While the results on the 2D CMR images are promising, in future investigated CNN-based models will be tested on other healthcare images such as Computer Tomography (CT), X-rays and/or Echocardiogram (Echos) images to determine the model's comprehensive diagnostic capabilities, cross-domain scalability, and performance on multi-model data.

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